

A comprehensive review of GIS-based landslide Susceptibility mapping on key influencing factors

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ABSTRACT

A landslide is a mass movement of material, such as rock, earth or debris, down a slope. It results in the loss of life, damage to the land, and infrastructure, and loss of natural resources. Landslides may occur due to natural processes or man-made activities. To minimize its risks, it is necessary to assess landslides susceptibility. Modern techniques that are used to study landslides include GIS and remote sensing in combination with modeling techniques. These techniques and software are widely used for the assessment and susceptibility of landslide mapping. This paper contains a review of nineteen research papers on the analysis of landslide susceptibility in the last 16 years. It comprises the study of different countries mainly Asian countries. The literature was examined for the locations of the case study, effectual parameters used, and results validation. The contributory factors for the analysis and modeling of landslide susceptibility assessment and mapping include slope, lithology, curvature, precipitation, and geology in most of the researches. It is also important to evaluate both anthropogenic and natural factors to study the landslides. This analysis also includes the techniques used for the landslide susceptibility mapping.

Keywords: Landslide, landslide susceptibility mapping, modelling and GIS

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1. Introduction

When natural or artificial slopes are subjected to mass wasting processes, landslide occurs. It is the motion of a rockmass, debris, or soil down a slope under the action of gravity [1]. Landslides comprises flow, slide, topple, fall or spread and some landslides exhibit a combination of different type of movements during the movement of a landslide. All continents are facing the concern of landslides. They play a crucial role in the formation of landscape. It is also a serious threat to population in many countries [2]. Landslides may be induced by natural activities or man-made actions. Among the natural factors inducing landslides are heavy rain, earthquake, rising groundwater, snowmelt, and stream erosion [3].

Identifying the susceptible zones to landslides and its possible prevention is necessary for the natural hazard mitigation and development plans. To evaluate the landslides susceptibility accurately it is necessary to consider both natural and anthropogenic factors [4]. GIS techniques and software are widely used to for landslide susceptibility assessment.

GIS is a system efficiently able in acquiring thematic maps from numerous sources. Using this system it is simple to handle and examine geographical data and present the results in the form of proper maps, graphs, and figures. Moreover it is also necessary to combine GIS techniques with models for an accurate assessment. The modeling techniques may be classified as qualitative and quantitative [4]. The most common models used frequently are frequency ratio model, validation by R-Index method [5].

Few evaluations have been found for GIS-based landslide susceptibility mapping approaches, even though in several researches these techniques were used to identify hazard zones and to assess the landslide susceptibility. Thus, the purpose of this review was to examine the articles that have been published in the past 16 years to investigate landslide susceptibility using remote sensing and GIS. To compare the locations of published studies and to identify the most determinant-inducing factors, the literature was specifically evaluated for this study. Figure 2 shows the location of case studies. Future research on geospatial modeling will benefit from a deeper understanding of the subject because of this evaluation study.

Figure 1. The selective factors with their frequencies

2. Methodology

To achieve the research objectives a systematic literature analysis was conducted following the standard guidelines. The keywords including landslides, geospatial analysis, and GIS-based landslides susceptibility mapping were searched on

international databases such as Google Scholar, Springer, and ScienceDirect for the published research papers in the past 16 years. After searching on these sources about 40 papers were found regarding the landslide studies based on GIS and remote sensing. However, the most relevant papers were preferred. Finally, 19 research papers were selected for the review. Landslides are mainly caused by natural and anthropogenic activities. In past papers, various landslides-inducing factors were taken into account by different authors. The papers were wisely reviewed for the enhancing factors. The papers were studied for the validation of results means whether the predictions are accurate or not.

3. Results and Discussion

In this study, 19 papers were reviewed from 2008 to 2024. Landslide susceptibility mapping and hazard zone classification using GIS has been a trending topic for research in the last few years. An accurate assessment and modeling are useful for the evaluation of landslide-inducing factors. Landslides may be induced naturally or artificially. Previous studies were based on various causing factors for such hazards. The predictions for such risks were mainly based on available data, similar studies, and expert opinion. Overall seven to thirteen factors were taken into account in the past researches. Here the most important and contributing factors are considered as show in the fig No. 1. Most of the factors are repeated in all papers. One of the most important factors that are considered in the papers is the slope followed by various factors like lithology, elevation, precipitation, and vegetation loss. Other important factors are distance to the road, distance from the river, and distance from faults. Land cover is also an important factor considered in the studies. Geology is also an important factor that affects landslide motion as presented in the literature. Here are some important factors that induce risks of landslides.

- a. **Slope:** Slope is the main component that that control the occurrence of landslides. The critical slope amplifies the effect of other landslide inducing factors. In a homogenous lithological setting with a consistent slope; a landslide is primarily is caused by an increase in slope [5]. Based on the review of many papers it is found that most of the landslides during past 16 years, it is found that angle between 20-25 degree contributes to the regional landslides improvement (Wu et al., 2010). Slope is acquired from the points of Global Positioning System (GPS), Digital Elevation Model (DEM) and topho-sheet maps. The most accurate and reliable method for finding the slope of an area is the use of DEM which is acquired from various sources like United States Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Explorer, **National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Earthdata, and OpenTopography**.
- b. **Lithology:** The physical properties of rocks such as resistance to the erosion is called lithology [7]. Rocks with high strength are resistive to soil erosion. Joint density also effects landslides occurrence. As the joint density in the formations decreases, the recurrence ratio of the landslide rises [8]. Therefore considering lithology for the landslide hazards is necessary. This factor is mainly acquired from geological maps of the study area, field data, aerial photographs, and satellite imageries. As per the literature review it is concluded that lithology is the second most important after the slope.
- c. **Elevation:** Although landslides happen at certain elevations with specific gradients, an elevated region's height causes an increased gradient, which raises the shear forces on slopes. Additionally, the high altitude encourages daily temperature

fluctuations, which, as a side effect, generate the necessary debris for the sliding phenomenon by causing weathering and the cryoclastic phenomenon [5]. Elevation takes 41% of the participants, among other factors.

- d. **Curvature:** The Curvature describes the landscape geomorphology. The maximal slope's trajectory is equivalent to profile curvature [9]. It is an important factor. It directs the water and landslide material [10].
- e. **Land Use Land Cover (LULC):** It is the prominent cover of the land surface by anthropogenic activities or the vegetation [11]. Different type of land Cover may have an impact on the stability of slopes. Because, LULC can alter the hydrological functioning of hillslopes, infiltration characteristics, runoff generation, and soil shear strength [12]. Land cover can be acquired from satellite imageries and remote sensing techniques. When DEM is interpreted by GIS land cover can be find out. The land cover is repeated over 10 times in the reviewed papers.
- f. **Geology:** Geology is an important factor in the evaluation of landslides. It is mainly studied on the basis of rock permeability [13]. The geological data for landslide affected areas are prepared from available geological maps and websites like USGS.
- g. **Distance from rivers:** The occurrence of landslides is specifically regulated by the distance to the river [14]. In the meantime, the following factors are principally responsible for the considerable impact of river erosion on the formation of landslides: (1) The strength of a rock mass is diminished by the softening effect of water. (2) The riverbank grows steep as a result of water erosion over time. (3) Hydrostatic pressure will be created on each side of the rock and soil by the tension fracture that is filled with surface water or groundwater, which is detrimental to the slope's stability. (4) The slope close to the valley will be significantly impacted by hydrodynamic pressure. (5) A landslide may develop as a result of the groundwater's buoyancy force acting on the slope base's free surface [15]. Distance from rivers can be found out by using satellite imageries and remote sensing. This factor is highly considered among the landslide inducing factors because, in the 19 reviewed papers it is frequented about 12 times.
- h. **Distance from faults:** The frequency of landslides is directly related to the distance to the fault [16]. A zone of deep and severe weathering inside the crust is formed when a weak structural plane within the faulted zone develops and causes rock fragmentation and weathering. Given that nearly every landslide occurs within a 1000-meter radius of the fault, the distance-to-fault map's computation interval is set at 200 meters [15]. Faults maps are created from geological maps and tectonic literature. In the reviewed papers this important factor is frequented about 11 times.
- i. **Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI):** NDVI elaborates the density of vegetation cover on earth. NDVI can be acquired using satellite imageries and remote sensing. Its value ranges from -1 to +1 with high positive NDVI value (green), which means high vegetation. Water has negative NDVI values (yellow and red). Urban features has 0 value [17]. Nine papers inquired this factor in the review which means that it is also important.
- j. **Rainfall:** Landslide risks are especially common during the rainy season because rainfall is one of the main elements that can cause a landslide [18]. Geological hazards occur when rainfall infiltration weakens the soil's shear strength and the friction that holds the soil and bedrock together. Nonetheless, there is a negligible difference in the study area's average precipitation between 230 and 280 mm. Rainfall is therefore not thought to be the most significant factor in sensitivity mapping [15].

It is also described in the research papers but not important as slope, curvature, faults or other landslide inducing factors.

Figure 2. Location of case studies

4. Result Validation

In landslide susceptibility mapping the validation of the result is an essential step in the assessment of accuracy of the predictions [19]. Most of the studies have validated the results using different models. Some of the models used are receiver operating characteristics (ROC), success rate curve (SRC), and Area under the curve (AUC) [15]. Other models are **logistic regression and machine learning techniques** [20]. **Most of the studies used Gradient Boosted Decision Trees (GBDT), support vector machine (SVM), and MARS** [21]. Some of the simple models used for the assessment of landslide susceptibility mapping are weighted overlay Model (WOM), and Frequency ration model (FRM) [22].

5. Conclusions

After reviewing the papers it was revealed how much landslides impact both rural and urban communities' facilities structures, and agricultural land. Due to this concern, numerous studies have been carried out worldwide, particularly in susceptible places, to estimate the vulnerability of landslides using GIS and models. The research demonstrated that GIS and remote sensing methods, when paired with other models, are effective and precise instruments for assessing the vulnerability of landslides. The landslide susceptibility maps are an invaluable resource for development projects, site selection, and land use planning as well as for reducing potential landslide impacts. By examining contributing factors such as slope, curvature, lithology, land use, rainfall, and proximity to rivers, the spatial patterns of the landslide were determined. In general, when choosing the factors, the data's availability was taken into account. Slope, plan curvature, lithology, and distance to streams were among the characteristics that were utilized in the majority of research. Additionally, the literature analysis demonstrated that rehabilitation and control methods should be taken into consideration for susceptible countries that have shown landslide accidents and were adequately considered.

Conflicts of Interest:

Author has no conflict of interest.

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